

SYNTHESIS OF 8-AMINOQUINOLINES. PART VIII

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Synthesis of 7-chloro-8-(1'-methyl-4'-diethylaminobutyl)-aminoquinoline has been described.

The substitution of a chlorine atom at the 7-position of 4-dialkylamino-alkyl-aminoquinolines in place of a 6-methoxy group affords compounds with enhanced antimalarial activity (Andersag, Breitner and Jung, Ger. Patent, 683,692/1939). In view of the above observation attempts were made to synthesise an analogue of Pamaquin having a 7-chloro substituent in place of the 6-methoxy group. Price and Guthrie (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1592) attempted to prepare the corresponding compound by the interaction of 7-chloro-8-aminoquinoline with the di-alkylamino-alkyl halides. But the reaction did not take place under the conditions tried.

In this laboratory an attempt was made to prepare this type of compounds by the interaction of the sodium derivative of 7-chloro-8-*p*-toluenesulphonamidoquinoline and appropriate aminoalkyl halides and detosylation of the product. Although the intermediate alkylamino-alkyl-*p*-toluenesulphonamidoquinolines were obtained in good yield, the detosylation of the compounds by the various known methods, including that of Weisblat *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1953, 75, 3630), could not be achieved. Even the use of lithium aluminium hydride for detosylation (cf. Karrer and Asmis, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 35, 1926) proved abortive.

7-Chloro-8-(1'-methyl-4'-diethylaminobutyl)-aminoquinoline was, however, prepared by a different route. 2:3-Dichloronitrobenzene was allowed to react with 1-diethyl-amino-4-aminopentane to afford 2-chloro-6-nitro-1'-methyl-4'-diethylaminobutylaniline. This was reduced with stannous chloride and the corresponding amine was subjected to the Skraup reaction to yield the desired product. The compound was isolated as the methylene-*bis*-salicylate.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Chloro-8-*p*-toluenesulphonamidoquinoline.—A mixture of 7-chloro-8-aminoquinoline (6 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (7 g.) and dry pyridine (10 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours. The mixture was poured into ice-water and the solid filtered, washed with water and dried. After crystallisation from alcohol the solid melted at 152°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 8.18. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2N_2ClS$ requires N, 8.42%).

Sodium Derivative.—The above compound (8 g.) was suspended in water (30 c.c.) and 10% NaOH solution (10 c.c.) was added. A white pasty mass was formed. Acetone was added to it, filtered, washed with acetone and dried at 100°, yield 8 g.

7-Chloro-8-N- γ -diethylaminopropyl-*p*-toluenesulphonamidoquinoline.—To the above sodium derivative (8 g.), suspended in dry toluene (100 c.c.), γ -chloropropyldiethylamine (5 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 14 hours in an oil-bath. Toluene

was distilled off. The residue was crystallised from ethanol in colorless micro-crystalline powder, m.p. 108-10°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 9.17%. $C_{23}H_{28}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.43%).

7-Chloro-8-N-β-diethylaminoethyl-p-toluenesulphonamidoquinoline was prepared similarly by allowing the sodium derivative of the sulphonamidoquinoline to react with β-diethylaminoethyl chloride, and it was crystallised from ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 109-10°. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{22}H_{26}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.73%).

2-Chloro-6-nitro-1'-methyl-4'-diethylamino-butylaniline.—A mixture of 2 : 3-dichloronitrobenzene (Kremer and Bendich, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2658) (10 g.) and 1-diethylamino-4-aminopentane (30 g.) was heated under reflux at 150-60° for 20 hours. The excess of unchanged amine was distilled off at 6 mm. The residue was dissolved in HCl (dil.) and the solution washed with ether. The aqueous solution was basified with NaOH and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure; 10 g. of the required amine was obtained as a reddish yellow oil boiling at 225-30°/6 mm. (Found: N, 13.38. $C_{15}H_{21}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 13.40%).

2-Chloro-6-amino-1'-methyl-4'-diethylamino-butylaniline.—To stannous chloride (35 g.) in HCl (conc., 50 c.c.) in a flask, cooled in an ice-bath, the above nitro compound (9 g.), dissolved in HCl (conc., 35 c.c.), was added. The flask was kept sometime in the cooling bath and then gradually heated to 70° when a clear solution was formed. The flask was heated at 80-90° for 2 hours and left overnight at room temperature. Next day, the reaction mixture was dissolved in warm water and poured into excess of iced alkali. The oily product was extracted with ether and the extract dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The solvent was distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to yield 6 g. of a light coloured viscous oil boiling at 208-14°/16 mm. (Found: N, 14.62. $C_{15}H_{25}N_2Cl$ requires N, 14.81%).

7-Chloro-8-(1'-methyl-4'-diethylaminobutyl)-aminoquinoline.—A mixture of the above amine (9 g.), dry glycerine (20 c.c.), arsenic pentoxide (6 g.) and H_2SO_4 (conc.) was cautiously heated at 160-70° for 8 hours. The reaction product was treated with ice and water, and charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was basified with caustic soda, extracted with ether and the ether extract dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. Ether was distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 180-200°/4-5 mm, yield 1 g.

Methylene-bis-salicylate.—To the above compound (1 g.), dissolved in absolute ethanol, methylene-bis-salicylic acid (2 g.), dissolved in ethanol, was added when an oily precipitate was formed. The precipitate was washed repeatedly with dry ether when it solidified. The solid was then dried *in vacuo* and finally over P_2O_5 at 100° at 6 mm., m.p. 110-12° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.4. $C_{18}H_{25}N_2Cl$. $C_{18}H_{13}O_6$ requires N, 6.91%).